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Data to the knowledge of the fauna of plume moths (Lepidoptera: Pterophoridae) of Georgia

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Abstract. An annotated list of species of Pterophoridae (Lepidoptera) from Georgia is compiled based on our material and literature data. The material was collected in 11 localities in 2022–2024. To date, 45 species of Pterophoridae are known from Georgia, 13 of which are recorded for the first time for the fauna of the country.

Key words: Lepidoptera, plume moths, biodiversity, Transcaucasia, Georgia.

Материалы к познанию фауны пальцекрылок (Lepidoptera: Pterophoridae) Грузии

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Резюме. Приведен аннотированный список видов Pterophoridae (Lepidoptera) Грузии на основе собственного материала и литературных данных. Материал был собран в 11 местонахождениях в 2022–2024 годах. На сегодняшний день в Грузии выявлено 45 видов пальцекрылок, 13 из которых впервые указаны для фауны страны.

Ключевые слова: Lepidoptera, пальцекрылки, биоразнообразие, Закавказье, Грузия.

Plume moths (Lepidoptera: Pterophoridae) of Georgia have been already mentioned by Arenberger [1995, 1998, 2002, 2005, 2007], Bigot and Picard [1996], Gielis [2003], Ustjuzhanin et al. [2015], Ustjuzhanin and Kovtunovich [2018], Nedoshivina et al. [2023] and Hobern [2024]. In total, 45 species of Pterophoridae have been identified to date, 13 of which are listed in this paper as new for the region.

Material and methods

The collection of Pterophoridae is the result of research during scientific expeditions to Georgia in 2022–2024, organized by the Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom (Poland) in cooperation with the Institute of Entomology, the Agricultural University of Georgia and the Ilia State University in Tbilisi and members of the Polish Entomological Society. Pterophoridae specimens were collected by the last author. Standard methods of moths trapping were used, including battery-powered black light traps (3 × 6 W) from dusk to dawn and mixed light screens (mix 2 × 250 W) and black light (8 V) from dusk to 3:00–4:00 a.m. All Pterophoridae were caught either on black light or on illuminating sheets with mixed light. The studies were conducted in the following 11 localities:

Bakuriani: Samtskhe-Javakheti Region, 41°44'N / 43°32'E, 2005 m.

Borjomi: Borjomi-Kharagauli National Park, 41°47'N / 43°14'E, 1005 m.

Chachuna: Chachuna Managed Reserve, 41°13'N / 45°58'E, 250 m.

Dalis (Dam): 41°17'N / 45°54'E, 320 m.

Didi Ateni (Fig. 1): 10 km S of Gori, 41°53'N / 44°5'E, 782 m.

Gudanii: Gudanii village, 42°32'N / 44°57'E, 1720 m.

Roshka: Roshka village, 74 km NE from Dusheti, 42°32'N / 44°57'E, 2005 m.

Vardzia (Fig. 2): 70 km S from Borjomi, 41°13'N / 45°58'E, 1270 m.

Mijniskure: Vashlovani National Park, 41°12'N / 46°23'E, 93 m.

Pantishara: Vashlovani National Park, 41°14'N / 46°21'E, 380 m.

Visitors Center (Fig. 3): Vashlovani National Park, 41°09'N / 46°34'E, 350 m.

The studied specimens are deposited in the collection of the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (St Petersburg, Russia), and in the private collections of the first two authors.

The species newly recorded for Georgia are marked with an asterisk.

**Agdistis adactyla* (Hübner, [1823])

Material. 1♂, Vardzia, 13–14.07.2023.

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, Caucasus, Siberia, Russian Far East), Georgia, Azerbaijan, Armenia, Turkey, Iran, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan,

Figs 1–3. Some localities of Pterophoridae in Georgia.

1 – Didi Ateni village, about 10 km south of Gori; 2 – Vardzia, the Kura River valley, southern Georgia near the border with Turkey; 3 – Visitors Center, Vashlovani National Park. Photographs by L. Matuszewski.

Рис. 1–3. Некоторые местонахождения Pterophoridae в Грузии.

1 – Диди-Атени, 10 км к югу от Гори; 2 – Вардзия, долина Куры на юге Грузии недалеко от границы с Турцией; 3 – Центр посетителей, национальный парк «Вашловани». Фотографии Л. Матушевского.

Kyrgyzstan, Tadzhikistan, Afghanistan, China (Beijing, Tianjin, Hebei, Inner Mongolia, Shaanxi, Gansu, Ningxia, Xinjiang), Mongolia [Gielis, 2003; Li et al., 2003; Hobern, 2024].

Agdistis caradjai Arenberger, 1975

= *Agdistis karabachica* Zagulajev, 1990.

Material. 1♂, Didi Ateni, 6–8.06.2022; 3♀, Visitors Center, 11.05.2023; 1♀, same place, 8.10.2023; 1♀, Pantishara, 12.05.2023; 1♂, Mijnskure, 14.04.2024.

Note. Recorded for Georgia as *Agdistis karabachica* [Nupponen, 2022].

Distribution. Russia (Dagestan), Georgia, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Turkmenistan [Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2018].

**Agdistis frankeniae* (Zeller, 1847)

Material. 2♂, Dalis (Dam), 30.05.2022; 1♀, Chachuna, 16–18.07.2023.

Distribution. Western Europe, European part of Russia, Russian Caucasus, Georgia, Azerbaijan, Asia Minor, Iran, Kazakhstan [Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2018].

**Agdistis ingens* Christoph, 1885

Material. 1♂, 1♀, Dalis (Dam), 30.05.2022; 1♂, Chachuna, 16–18.07.2023.

Distribution. The south-east of the European part of Russia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Afghanistan, China (Gansu), Mongolia [Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2016].

Agdistis sissia Arenberger, 1987

Material. 1♀, Didi Ateni, 30.05.2022; 9 ex., same place, 6–8.06.2022; 9 ex., Vardzia, 2–5.06.2022; 5 ex., Visitors Center, 11.05.2023.

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Nupponen [2022].

Distribution. Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Iran, Turkmenistan [Hobern, 2024].

Paraplatyptilia metzneri (Zeller, 1841)

Material. 1♀, Vardzia, 2–5.06.2022; 1♂, same place, 13–14.07.2023; 1♂, Gudanii, 20.07.2023; 1♂, Didi Ateni, 23–24.07.2023.

Note. Recorded for South Ossetia by Nedoshivina et al. [2023].

Distribution. Europe, Russia (European part, Caucasus, South Ural, southern Siberia), Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Asia Minor, Iran, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Northwestern China, Mongolia [Gielis, 2003; Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2019; Hobern, 2024].

**Platyptilia calodactyla*
(Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775)

Material. 1♂, Bakuriani, 15.07.2023.

Distribution. North Africa, Western Europe, Russia (European part, Siberia, Far East), Georgia, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Middle Asia, China, Mongolia [Ustjuzhanin, 1996].

**Platyptilia gonodactyla*
(Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775)

Material. 1♂, Didi Ateni, 23–24.07.2023.

Distribution. North Africa, Western Europe, Russia (European part, Siberia, Russian Far East), Georgia, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Middle Asia, China (Xinjiang), Mongolia [Ustjuzhanin, 1996].

Gillmeria pallidactyla (Haworth, 1811)

Material. 1♂, Vardzia, 13–14.07.2023; 1♂, Roshka, 21–22.07.2023.

Note. Recorded for South Ossetia by Nedoshivina et al. [2023].

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, Caucasus, Ural, Siberia, Far East), Georgia, Armenia,

Iran, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, China, Korea, Japan, North and South America [Hobern, 2024].

Amblyptilia acanthadactyla (Hubner, [1813])

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Arenberger [1998].

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, Caucasus, Siberia, Far East), Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, China (Jiangsu), Mongolia, Japan [Ustuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2012; Ustuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2019; Hobern, 2024].

Amblyptilia punctidactyla (Haworth, 1811)

Material. 1♀, Gudanii, 20.07.2023; 1♂, Vardzia, 9–10.04.2024.

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Bigot and Picard [1996].

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, Caucasus, Siberia, Far East), Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, China (Jiangsu), Mongolia, Japan [Ustuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2012], Canada, USA [Arenberger, 2007].

Cnaemidophorus rhododactyla
(Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775)

Material. 5 ex., Vardzia, 13–14.07.2023.

Note. Recorded for South Ossetia by Nedoshivina et al. [2023].

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, Caucasus, Ural, Siberia, Far East), Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Iran, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Pakistan, India, China, Korea, Japan, North America [Hobern, 2024].

Stenoptilia arida (Zeller, 1847)

Material. 1♂, Visitors Center, 12.05.2023; 1♀, Didi Ateni, 23–24.07.2023.

Note. Recorded for South Ossetia by Nedoshivina et al. [2023].

Distribution. North Africa, Southern Europe, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Afghanistan [Ustuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2018; Hobern, 2024].

Stenoptilia bipunctidactyla (Scopoli, 1763)

Material. 2♂, Borjomi, 5.06.2022.

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Bigot and Picard [1996].

Distribution. North Africa, Western Europe, Russia (European part, Polar Ural, southern Siberia, Far East: south of Primorskiy Region), Georgia, Israel, Iran, Mongolia [Ustuzhanin et al., 2020; Ustuzhanin, Maksimov, 2023].

Stenoptilia dolini Arenberger, 2007

Distribution. Georgia [Arenberger, 2007].

Stenoptilia graphodactyla (Treitschke, 1833)

Note. Recorded for South Ossetia by Nedoshivina et al. [2023].

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, Siberia), Georgia, Armenia, Kazakhstan, China (Shanxi, Xinjiang) [Ustuzhanin et al., 2015].

**Stenoptilia mannii* (Zeller, 1852)

Material. 6 ex., Gudanii, 20.07.2023.

Distribution. Morocco, Southern Europe, Russia (south of the European part, Dagestan), Azerbaijan, Armenia, Turkey, Syria, Israel, Iraq, Iran, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Pakistan [Arenberger, 2005; Ustuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2019], Georgia.

**Stenoptilia pneumonantes* (Buttner, 1880)

Material. 1♀, Roshka, 21–22.07.2023.

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, southern Siberia, Yakutia), Georgia, Kazakhstan, China (Xinjiang) [Arenberger, 2005].

**Stenoptilia poculi* Arenberger, 1998

Material. 1♀, Gudanii, 20.07.2023.

Distribution. North Caucasus (Russia: Kabardino-Balkarian Republic), Georgia, Armenia [Arenberger, 2005; Ustuzhanin et al., 2015].

Stenoptilia pterodactyla (Linnaeus, 1761)

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Bigot and Picard [1996].

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, Caucasus, Siberia, Far East (?)), Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, North America [Ustuzhanin, 1996; Arenberger, 2005].

Stangeia siceliota (Zeller, 1847)

Note. Recorded for South Ossetia by Nedoshivina et al. [2023].

Distribution. Western Europe, Georgia, Armenia, Turkey, Syria, Lebanon, Israel, Jordan, Saudi Arabia, Yemen, Iraq, Iran [Ustuzhanin et al., 2015], Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, Afghanistan, China (Hunan) [Arenberger, 2002].

Procopperia kuldschaensis (Rebel, 1914)

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Arenberger [2002].

Distribution. Ukraine, Russia (South Ural, Altai, Kemerovo, Tuva, Khakassia), Georgia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Afghanistan, Pakistan, China (Xinjiang), Mongolia [Ustuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2016].

Procopperia linariae (Chretien, 1922)

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Ustuzhanin et al. [2015].

Distribution. Southern Europe, Russia (Crimea, southern part of European Russia, Caucasus), Georgia, Armenia, Asia Minor [Ustuzhanin et al., 2015].

Procapperia maculata (Constant, 1865)

Material. 1♂, 1♀, Didi Ateni, 6–8.06.2022; 5 ex., same place, 23–24.07.2023.

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Arenberger [1998].

Distribution. Southern Europe, Ukraine, Armenia, Asia Minor [Ustjuzhanin et al., 2015], Georgia.

Paracapperia anatolica (Caradja, 1920)

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Bigot and Picard [1996].

Distribution. Georgia, Armenia, Turkey, Syria, Iran, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan [Hobern, 2024].

**Capperia celeusi* (Frey, 1886)

Material. 2♂, Vardzia, 2–5.06.2022; 7 ex., 13–14.07.2023; 5 ex., Visitors Center, 8.10.2023.

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (southern part of European Russia, Caucasus, Ural), Armenia, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Lebanon, Iran, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan [Hobern, 2024], Georgia.

Capperia maratonica Adamczewski, 1951

Material. 1♀, Pantishara, 29.05.2023.

Note. Recorded for South Ossetia by Nedoshivina et al. [2023].

Distribution. Southern Europe, Ukraine, Russia (Crimea, Caucasus), Georgia, Armenia, Turkey, Israel, Turkmenistan [Hobern, 2024].

Capperia salanga Arenberger, 1995

Note. Recorded for South Ossetia by Nedoshivina et al. [2023].

Distribution. Georgia, Turkey, Iran, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Afghanistan [Arenberger, 2002].

Crombrugghia distans (Zeller, 1847)

Material. 1♀, Dalis (Dam), 30.05.2022; 3 ex., Vardzia, 2–5.06.2022; 1♂, same place, 13–14.07.2023; 7 ex., Didi Ateni, 6–8.06.2022.

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Bigot and Picard [1996].

Distribution. Canary Islands, North Africa, Western Europe, Ukraine, Russia (Crimea, European part, Caucasus, southern Siberia), Georgia, Armenia, Turkey, Iran, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Afghanistan, Pakistan, India, Nepal, China (Xinjiang) [Arenberger, 2002; Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2019; Hobern, 2024].

Oxyptilus parvidactylus (Haworth, 1811)

Note. Recorded for South Ossetia by Nedoshivina et al. [2023].

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, West Siberia), Georgia, Armenia, Turkey, Syria, Israel, Iran [Arenberger, 2002; Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2019; Hobern, 2024].

Oxyptilus pilosellae (Zeller, 1841)

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Bigot and Picard [1996].

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, Caucasus, South Ural), Georgia, Turkey, Iran, Kazakhstan [Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2019; Hobern, 2024].

Pselnophorus poggei (Mann, 1862)

Material. 1♂, Bakuriani, 15.07.2023.

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Gielis [2003].

Distribution. Ukraine, southern part of European Russia, Russian Caucasus, Georgia, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Iran [Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2019; Hobern, 2024].

Hellinsia didactylites (Strom, 1783)

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Bigot and Picard [1996].

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, Caucasus, South Ural, Siberia, Far East), Georgia, Armenia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, China (Shaanxi, Jilin) [Hobern, 2024].

Hellinsia osteodactyla (Zeller, 1841)

Material. 1♂, Gudanii, 20.07.2023; 1♂, Roshka, 21–22.07.2023.

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Bigot and Picard [1996].

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, Siberia, Far East), Georgia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, China (Heilongjiang, Shandong, Shanxi, Xinjiang, Yunnan, Ningxia), Mongolia, Japan [Li et al., 2003; Hobern, 2024].

Hellinsia tephrodactyla (Hübner, [1813])

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Bigot and Picard [1996].

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, Caucasus, South Ural, Siberia, Transbaikalia, Yakutia, Kamchatka), Georgia [Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2019].

**Oidaematophorus lithodactylus* (Treitschke, 1833)

Material. 1♀, Didi Ateni, 23–24.07.2023.

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, Caucasus, Southern Ural, Siberia, Far East), Georgia, Turkey, Iran, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, China (Xinjiang), Japan [Li et al., 2003; Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2019].

Emmelina monodactyla (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material. 1♀, Didi Ateni, 6–8.06.2022; 6 ex., same place, 23–24.07.2023; 2♀, Pantishara, 12.05.2023; 1♀, same place, Pantishara, 29.05.2023; 6 ex., Vardzia, 13–14.07.2023; 17 ex., same place, 9–10.04.2024; 1♂, Chachuna, 16–18.07.2023; 2♀, 1♂, Gudanii, 20.07.2023; 5 ex., Visitors Center, 4.10.2023.

Note. Recorded for South Ossetia by Nedoshivina et al. [2023].

Distribution. North Africa, Western Europe, Russia (European part, Siberia east to Tuva), Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, India, China, Mongolia, Philippines, North and South America [Ustjuzhanin et al., 2017].

Emmeline pseudojezonica Derra, 1987

Note. Recorded for Georgia as *Emmeline argoteles* by Bigot and Picard [1996].

Distribution. Western Europe, southern part of European Russia, Azerbaijan [Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2018].

Adaina microdactyla (Hübner, [1813])

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Bigot and Picard [1996].

Distribution. Western Europe, southern part of European Russia, Georgia, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Israel, Iran, Nepal, China, Japan, Vietnam, Philippines, Indonesia, New Guinea, Solomon Islands, tropical and subtropical Africa, Madagascar [Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2018].

Calyciphora nephelodactyla (Eversmann, 1844)

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Gielis [2003].

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, Caucasus, South Ural), Georgia, Turkey, Syria [Gielis, 2003; Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2019].

**Tabulaephorus decipiens* (Lederer, 1870)

Material. 1♀, Didi Ateni, 23–24.07.2023.

Distribution. Russian Caucasus, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan [Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2018], Georgia.

Merrifieldia leucodactyla
([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775)

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Arenberger [2007].

Distribution. North Africa, Western Europe, Russia (European part, Southern Ural, Siberia, Yakutia, Far East), Georgia, Armenia, Turkey, Iran, Kazakhstan, China (Shanxi), Mongolia [Bigot, Picard, 1996; Hobern, 2024].

**Merrifieldia tridactyla* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material. 3♂, 1♀, Didi Ateni, 6–8.06.2022.

Distribution. Western Europe, Russia (European part, Southern Ural, south of West Siberia, western Yakutia), Georgia, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Iran, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan [Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2018].

**Wheeleria obsoleta* (Zeller, 1841)

Material. 1♂, Didi Ateni, 6–8.06.2022.

Distribution. Southern Europe, Ukraine, Russia (southern part of European Russia, Dagestan), Armenia, Turkey, Jordan, Iran, Turkmenistan [Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2018], Georgia.

Pterophorus pentadactylus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material. 1♂, Vardzia, 13–14.07.2023; 1♂, Gudanii, 20.07.2023.

Note. Recorded for Georgia by Bigot and Picard [1996].

Distribution. Western Europe, Ukraine, Russia (European part, Caucasus, West Siberia, Far East),

Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Israel, Iran, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, China (Jilin, Sichuan, Yunnan, Xinjiang, Taiwan), Mongolia [Li et al., 2003; Ustjuzhanin, Kovtunovich, 2011; Hobern, 2024].

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